

**Public Wartime Diaries from Ukraine (2022-2026)
Building a Corpus Inventory and Methodological Documentation**

Research Project Description

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Project focus, objectives, and broader research perspective

My project deals with rich yet under-systematized type of wartime testimony – **public diaries**, which I define as a sub-genre of life writing – longitudinal, first-person accounts published as physical volumes or continuously maintained on digital platforms and intentionally shared with an audience in real-time or shortly after events.

While falling into the broad category of grassroots real-time documentation alongside chat messages, social media posts, and witness interviews, public diaries occupy a distinct position. As a literary form, they tend to attract authors capable of sustained reflection and articulation than other documentary forms. They unfold as long-form narration and maintain stronger continuity than shorter social media posts. Finally, they circulate across heterogeneous media – printed books and digital platforms – creating more scattered documentation landscape than other sources. All of this results in a specific form of documentation: a durable yet dispersed body of texts, circulating across media and often citing or responding to one another.

Read together as a *corpus*, public diaries cease to be singular, isolated voices. They become a networked record of social practice – a "living archive" in the truest sense – where the value of the whole exceeds the sum of its parts and where inquiry shifts to a different level: how meanings

circulate across many lives and places during the same historical process – rather than how individual writers experience it.

Yet while corpus-based research is well-established for interviews or social network posts, applying it to diaries remains rare. Because of their longitudinal depth, temporal non-linearity, and existence across fragmented media, diaries actively resist simple aggregation and require methodological articulation to transform scattered texts into an analytical corpus.

Despite the abundance of individual diaries – roughly, over 200 published volumes in English, 60+ in Ukrainian, 100+ long-form projects on Substack, Medium, and Ghost, and hundreds of Facebook projects – this methodological work remains undone. What is missing is curated collections of *diaries only*, systematic approaches to working with such corpora, and epistemological perspectives to underpin their analysis across authors, places, and time.

My project addresses this gap through **two objectives**:

1. To create an open-access digital corpus inventory of public diaries documenting Russia's war against Ukraine, 2022-2026 (hereinafter *the Corpus*) – a comprehensive, annotated, searchable reference collection of public wartime diaries, both published volumes and digital, with with statistical visualization and metadata enabling systematic comparison across authors, locations, temporal periods, and platforms.

2. To develop and share methodological documentation articulating the specific technical stages and interpretive procedures required to transform scattered diary texts into a cohesive analytical corpus suitable for systematic research.

While empirically grounded in wartime diaries from Ukraine, this project's methodological contribution extends beyond the Ukrainian case. The diary-as-corpus approach being developed here is transferable to other contexts of wartime staying – from other conflict zones to occupied territories where communities document their experiences in real time.

Current status of the project

Having already begun preliminary work on this corpus, I have:

- Defined operational criteria for "public diaries" and identified over 60 published and digital sources across multiple platforms (Substack, Medium, Ghost, Facebook, Threads).
- Begun collecting full-text diary entries and designed the metadata structure for the Corpus.
- Developed a pilot coding framework in MAXQDA to test the technical feasibility of the corpus-based approach to public diaries (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18040135>).

The Corpus architecture

The Corpus will be built on *Omeka CMS*, hosted on the commercial hosting (which I maintain for my personal and projects websites) as a part of the broader website of my research program addressing those who stay in their homelands during durable disruptions (<http://thestayer.org>).

The Corpus will be located on a dedicated subdomain *corpus.thestayr.org* to ensure easy and stable long-term access.

To ensure interoperability, the Corpus will be kept compliant with FAIR principles and Dublin Core metadata standards. It will be accompanied with statistical visualization of the documentation landscape – geographic distribution of authors, temporal intensity of writing, and platform migration – providing an immediate overview of the diary corpus structure.

This architecture is inspired by the [365 Days of War](#) project (Kule Folklore Center, University of Alberta). It accumulates institutional initiatives collecting oral histories, but the general architecture is perfect also for a reference base of the primary sources – individual diaries.

Planned outcomes / deliverables

The fellowship will yield an **evolving sequence of deliverables**, allowing me to **squeeze the maximum value out of a single work**. This trajectory moves from the Diary Corpus itself to methodological documentation and further to several public talks, scholarly paper, and a blog post.

1. The Corpus: an open-access curated research corpus inventory of public wartime diaries documenting Russia's war against Ukraine (2022–2026), providing a structured reference point for future historical, sociological, and interdisciplinary research on wartime narratives through public diaries. *Where:* [project website](#), separate subdomain.

2. Visibility and cataloguing: submitting the project to catalogues of documentation initiatives: [The Most Documented War](#) (Center's for Urban History Catalogue of Documenting Initiatives), [Russia's War on Ukraine Archive](#) (Ukrainian Research Institute at Harvard University), and [the Qualitative Data Archive at IFiS PAN](#).

3. Methodological documentation: formal report detailing the stages of corpus construction and use – a transparent roadmap for others working with wartime diaries. *Where:* [project's website](#) and [project's Zenodo repository](#).

4. Herder Institute engagement: a presentation at the Herder Institute during the July research visit, and a blog post for the Herder Institute Blog within the "From the Perspective of a Fellow" series.

5. Conference presentations: During the fellowship period and the month following, I will participate in four international conferences and summer schools, and I will incorporate relevant insights from this project into my presentations.

6. Scholarly publication: source-description article focusing on the epistemological and methodological aspects of construction and interpretive study of diary corpora exemplified by the ongoing war in Ukraine. *Where:* Life Writing (ISSN 1448-4528) or European Journal of Life Writing (ISSN 2211-243X).

Resources

Citable description of this project: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19709376>

The Stayer project website: <http://thestayer.org>

The Stayer project repository: <https://zenodo.org/communities/thestayer>